

BUGUNGI MASHXUR DIETLARNING SPOR TUSHUNCHASIGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya. Har bir yoshdagi har bir kishi uchun muhim bo'lgan ovqatlanish, shuningdek, sportchilarning umumiy salomatligini saqlash, jismoniy tayyorgarlik va chidamlilikni oshirish, uzoq muddatli mashqlar samaradorligini oshirish va eng muhimi, muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun juda muhimdir. Har bir sportchining ovqatlanishi o'ziga xosdir.

Muvaffaqiyatga erishish yo'lida sportchilar o'zlarining murabbiylarini, do'stlarini, muvaffaqiyatli va / yoki mashhur sportchilarni misol qilib oladilar va turli xil ovqatlanish amaliyotlarini qo'llaydilar. Biroq, turli sabablarga ko'ra tanani shakllantirish, yog 'yoqishini tezlashtirish, ba'zi axloqiy fikrlar va diniy e'tiqodlarning ta'siri, vegan, vegetarian, ketogen va intervalgacha ro'za tutish dietalari ham sportchilar orasida mashhur bo'lib, ularni qo'llash ko'rsatkichlari ortib bormoqda. Ushbu parhezlarining tarqalishi ortib borayotganligi sababli, ushbu mavzu bo'yicha tadqiqotlar kuchayib bormoqda va mashhur parhezlarining sport ko'rsatkichlari va salomatlik holatiga ta'siri o'rganilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada, bugungi kunda sportchilar orasida mashhur bo'lgan parhezlarining mazmuni, ularning sportchining sog'lig'i va ishlashiga ta'siri va ushbu dietalarni qo'llashda e'tiborga olinishi kerak bo'lgan ovqatlanish tamoyillari, shu jumladan, mashhur parhezlar haqida keng qamrovli muhokama qilingan. .

Kalit so'zlar: Ommabop dietalar, sportchi, sport ko'rsatkichlari, jismoniy tarbiya, ovqatlanish.

THE INFLUENCE OF TODAY'S POPULAR DIETS ON THE CONCEPT OF SPORTS

Abstract. Nutrition, which is important for everyone of all ages, is also critical to athletes' overall health, fitness and endurance, long-term exercise performance, and, most importantly, success. Each athlete's diet is unique. On the road to success, athletes follow the example of their coaches, friends, successful and/or famous athletes, and adopt different nutritional practices.

However, for various reasons such as body building, fat burning, some moral considerations and the influence of religious beliefs, vegan, vegetarian, ketogenic and intermittent fasting diets are also popular among athletes. usage rates are increasing. As the prevalence of these diets increases, research on this topic is increasing and the effects of popular diets on athletic performance and health status are being investigated. This article provides an extensive overview of popular diets, including the content of diets popular among athletes today, their impact on athlete health and performance, and nutritional principles to consider when using these diets. is discussed comprehensively.

Key words: Popular diets, athlete, sports performance, physical education, nutrition.

ВЛИЯНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПОПУЛЯРНЫХ ДИЕТОВ НА ПОНЯТИЕ О СПОРТЕ

Аннотация. Питание, важное для всех людей всех возрастов, также необходимо спортсменам для поддержания общего состояния здоровья, улучшения физической формы и выносливости, улучшения долговременных физических показателей и, самое главное,

достижения успеха. Диета каждого спортсмена уникальна. На пути к успеху спортсмены следуют примеру своих тренеров, друзей, успешных и/или известных спортсменов и перенимают различные методы питания. Однако по разным причинам, таким как бодибилдинг, сжигание жира, некоторые моральные соображения и влияние религиозных убеждений, среди спортсменов также растет популярность веганских, вегетарианских, кетогенных диет и периодического голодания. Поскольку распространенность этих диет увеличивается, исследования по этой теме увеличиваются, и изучается влияние популярных диет на спортивные результаты и состояние здоровья. В этой статье представлен обширный обзор популярных диет, включая содержание диет, популярных сегодня среди спортсменов, их влияние на здоровье и работоспособность спортсменов, а также всесторонне обсуждаются принципы питания, которые следует учитывать при использовании этих диет.

Ключевые слова: Популярные диеты, спортсмен, спортивные результаты, физическое воспитание, питание.

KIRISH

Ko'rinib turibdiki, qadim zamonlardan to hozirgi kungacha insoniyatning asosiy ehtiyojlaridan biri bo'lgan va asosan uglevodlar, oqsillar va yog'larni o'z ichiga olgan oziqlanishning mazmuni, manbasi va tarkibida farqlar keltirib, ko'plab oziqa turlari paydo bo'lgan.

Oziqlanish turlari millionlab odamlar tomonidan ta'qib qilingan tendentsiyaga aylandi.

Yog 'yoqilishini tezlashtirish, tana idrokining o'zgarishi natijasida tanani shakllantirish, ba'zi axloqiy fikrlar va diniy e'tiqodlarning ta'siri, ayniqsa vegan, vegetarian, ketogen va intervalgacha ro'za tutish kabi turli sabablarga ko'ra butun dunyoda e'tiborni tortadi va amalga oshiriladi. Ushbu parhezlarni qo'llash darajasi o'z ovqatlanishida o'zgarishlar qilishni va o'z murabbiylarini, do'stlarini, muvaffaqiyatli va / yoki mashhur sportchilarni muvaffaqiyatga erishish yo'lida misol qilib olishni xohlaydigan sportchilar orasida oshdi. Vegan, vegetarian, ketogen va intervalgacha ro'za tutish dietalari haqida hozirgi ma'lumotlar quyida keltirilgan.

VEGAN OZIQLANISH

Vegan ovqatlanish; Bu go'sht, baliq, parranda go'shti va hayvonlar tomonidan ishlab chiqarilgan sut, tuxum va asal kabi oziq-ovqatlar iste'mol qilinmaydigan dietadir. Hozirgi vaqtda resurslardan yaxshiroq foydalanish va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish, hayvonlarni parvarish qilishdagi axloqiy muammolar, gormonlar va antibiotiklardan foydalanishning ko'payishi, hayvonlardan yuqadigan kasalliklarning ko'payishi, allergiya kabi turli sabablarga ko'ra vegan oziqlanish eng tez o'sib borayotgan tendentsiyalardan biriga aylandi. sut mahsulotlari salohiyati, laktoza intoleransi va tana vaznini nazorat qilishni ta'minlash. 2014 yildan 2018 yilgacha AQShda vegetarianlar soni 600% foizga oshdi. Bu tendentsiya sport va fitnes sanoatida ham kuzatildi, ko'plab sportchilar vegetarianlar parheziga rioya qilishni boshladilar. Shu tarzda, sifatli vegan mahsulotlar va vegan oziqaviy qo'shimchalar ko'paydi va vegan oziqlanish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar ham tezlashdi.

Sportchining sog'lig'i va ishlashiga ta'siri Vegan sportchilarning dietasi tekshirilganda; sabzavot, mevalar, murakkab uglevodlar, chidamli kraxmal va tolalarni ko'proq iste'mol qilish;

Xolesterin, to'yingan yog'lar va trans yog'larni iste'mol qilish kamroq ekanligi aniqlandi.

Shuningdek, vegan sportchilarning ratsionida ishqorlanish darajasi yuqoriroq va ular iste'mol qiladigan allergen tarkibiy qismlar kamroq bo'lishi kuzatilgan. Oziqlanishdagi ushbu o'zgarishlar bilan vegetarian sportchilar yurak-qon tomir / ishemik yurak kasalliklari tufayli morbidlik va o'lim xavfiga omnivor sportchilarga qaraganda kamroq duchor bo'lishlari aniqlandi.

Ta'kidlanishicha, vegan sportchilarning insulinga sezgirligi yaxshi bo'lib, keyingi hayotda 2-toifa diabet, metabolik sindrom va semirib ketish xavfi kamayadi. O'simlik ovqatlarini iste'mol qiladigan sportchilarning sistolik va diastolik qon bosimi hamma bilan oziqlanadigan sportchilarnikidan past ekanligi aniqlandi. Shuningdek, vegan oziqlanish oksidlovchi stressni kamaytiradi, endotelial funktsiyani yaxshilaydi, LDL xolesterin va umumiy xolesterin miqdorini kamaytiradi, yallig'lanish belgilarini pasaytiradi va immunitet belgilarini oshiradi. Vegan parhezlar ishqoriy muhit yaratib, mushaklardagi kislotalikni muvozanatlashi so'nggi yillarda ta'kidlangan muhim masaladir. Biroq, to'g'ri rejalashtirilmagan vegetarian parhezlar turli kasalliklar, ayniqsa osteoporoz xavfini oshirishi mumkinligini e'tiborsiz qoldirmaslik kerak. Vegan, lakto-ovovegetarian va omnivor yuguruvchilar baholangan tadqiqotda sportchilarning mashg'ulotlar chastotasi, davomiyligi, yugurish masofasi va maksimal quvvati o'rtasida sezilarli farq kuzatilmadi. Vegetarianlar va omnivor sportchilarni taqqoslagan boshqa tadqiqotda vegan sportchilar chap qorincha diametri kattaroq va V02max darajasi yuqoriroq ekanligi aniqlandi.

Vegan sportchilarning ovqatlanishi

Energiya, oqsil va mikroelementlar tarkibiga e'tibor qaratib tayyorlangan vegan parhezlar ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Chunki vegetarian parhezlar C va E vitaminlari, polifenollar bilan antioksidant tarkibiga ega va sport ko'rsatkichlari uchun muhim bo'lgan glikogen zahiralari ko'paytiruvchi uglevodlarga boy. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, vegetarianlar omnivorlarga qaraganda kamroq energiya iste'mol qiladilar. Buning muhim sabablaridan biri shundaki, o'simlikka asoslangan parhezlar past energiya zichligiga ega, ammo yuqori tolalar zichligi tufayli erta to'yinganlikni ta'minlaydi. Bu vazn yo'qotmoqchi bo'lgan sportchilarga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatada, ideal vaznda bo'lgan va energiyaga yuqori ehtiyojga ega bo'lgan sportchilar uchun kamchilikdir. Sportchilarning ovqatlanishi ularning ehtiyojlariga qarab tartibga solinishi kerak.

Ovqatlanish paytida yong'oq va yong'oq kabi energiya zichligi yuqori bo'lgan oziq-ovqatlarni iste'mol qilishni oshirish energiya ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun yaxshi tanlovdir.

Energiya balansidan tashqari, oqsil muvozanatini saqlash ham juda muhimdir. Hayvon manbalarini ratsionga kiritmaslik natijasida dietalar protein, ayniqsa BCAA jihatidan yyetarli bo'lmasligi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, o'simlik oqsillarining hazm bo'lishi hayvon oqsillariga qaraganda past bo'lganligi sababli, iste'mol qilinadigan miqdorni diqqat bilan aniqlash kerak.

Yulaf, quinoa, tofu, yasmiq, qora loviya, no'xat, bodom va qovoq urug'lari vegan sportchilar tomonidan afzal ko'rilishi mumkin bo'lgan protein manbalaridir. Proteinli qo'shimchalar ham tez-tez talab qilinadi. Energiya va oqsil nuqtai nazaridan dietani to'g'ri rejalashtirish vegan sportchilar uchun juda muhimdir.

VEGETERIYAN OZIQLANISH

O'simliklarga asoslangan ovqatlanish asosida; Lakto-vegetarian va laktovo-vegetarian kabi navlarga ega bo'lgan vegetarian ovqatlanish vegetarian oziqlanishga o'xshash sabablarga ko'ra tobora ommalashib bormoqda. U ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi, chunki u vegetarian dietasi kabi qat'iy qoidalarga ega emas, odatda tuxum va sut kabi boy protein manbalarini o'z ichiga oladi va ko'proq

uglevodlar, vitaminlar, minerallar, antioksidantlar, tolalar va sog'liq uchun zararli bo'lgan turli komponentlarni o'z ichiga oladi. omnivor dietalar. Ushbu boy tarkibga asoslangan to'g'ri rejalashtirilgan vegetarian parhezlar; Metabolik sindrom, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, diabet, semirib ketish xavfi va saraton kasalligini kamaytirishi mumkin.

Sportchi salomatligi va samaradorligiga ta'siri

Omnivor va vegetarian sportchilarni o'rgangan tadqiqotda tana vazni va tana massasi indeksi (BMI) vegetarianlar bilan solishtirganda omnivor hayvonlarda sezilarli darajada yuqori ekanligi aniqlandi. Guruhlar o'rtasida umumiy energiya, jami yog' va to'yingan yog'larni iste'mol qilishda farqlar yo'q edi, ammo vegetarian sportchilarda uglevodlarni iste'mol qilish sezilarli darajada yuqori edi. Jami protein iste'moli, protein hazm bo'lish ko'rsatkichi va mavjud protein balansi vegetarianlar bilan solishtirganda hamma bilan oziqlanadigan sportchilarda yuqori ekanligi aniqlandi. Quvvat o'lchovlarida sezilarli farqlar yo'q edi. O'simlikka asoslangan parhezga ega sportchilar va aralash dietaga ega sportchilarni taqqoslagan tadqiqotda, ikki guruh sportchilari o'rtasida aerob yoki anaerob ko'rsatkichlarida hech qanday farq topilmadi va vegetarian dietasi rejalashtirilganda sport samaradorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmasligi ta'kidlandi. to'g'ri.

KETOGENIK OVQATLANISH

Sport ovqatlanishining asosi uglevodlarni yyetarli miqdorda iste'mol qilishdir. Bundan tashqari, uglevodlarni yuklash musobaqalar davrida sportchining ish faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun qo'llaniladigan ozuqaviy strategiyalardan biridir. Ketogenik parhez - bu energiya muvozanatini ta'minlash uchun uglevodlar 50 grammdan past bo'lgan va yog' miqdori ko'paytiriladigan oziqlanish strategiyasidir. Ushbu strategiyaning asosi ketoz orqali tanadagi yog'larning parchalanishini oshirish orqali kerakli energiya bilan ta'minlashga harakat qilishdir.

So'nggi yillarda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarda; Inson tanasining cheklangan uglevodlarni saqlash qobiliyatiga qaramay, glyukoza oksidlanishi bilan energiya ishlab chiqarish o'n bir bosqichni oladi va energiya ishlab chiqarish parchalanishi bilan sodir bo'ladi.

Sportchi salomatligi va samaradorligiga ta'siri

Meta-tahlil shuni ko'rsatdiki, chidamlilik sportchilari 28 kunlik ketogenik parhezga (KD) moslashgandan so'ng, chidamlilik qobiliyatida pasayish kuzatilmagan va 21-84 kunlik moslashishdan keyin ularning chidamlilik ko'rsatkichlarida pasayish kuzatilmagan.

Tayyorlangan gimnastikachilar va taekvondochilarda 3-4 haftalik ketogenik parhezdan so'ng chidamlilik, kuch va izometrik quvvatning pasayishi kuzatilmadi. Boshqa bir guruh sportchilarda 21 kunlik KD bilan 2000 m masofaga yugurish ko'rsatkichlariga ijobiy ta'sirlar aniqlandi.

31 kunlik ketogenik parhezning submaksimal mashqlar qobiliyati va samaradorligiga ta'sirini o'rgangan tadqiqotda umumiy mashqlar vaqti, VO₂ max va nafas olish koeffitsienti o'rtasida sezilarli farq kuzatilmadi va ketogenik parhez o'rtacha submaksimal mashqlar qobiliyatini saqlab qolganligi ta'kidlandi.

KETOGENIK DIETADA OVQATLANISH TAMOYILLARI

O'n ikki haftalik ketogenik parhezdan so'ng, chidamlilik sportchilarida korpuskulyar gemoglobin va korpuskulyar gemoglobinning o'rtacha kontsentratsiyasi kamaydi. Bu holat sportchilarning ishlashi uchun katta xavf tug'dirishi mumkin. Shu sababli, KDni qo'llaydigan sportchilar; Qizil qon tanachalarini kuzatish va kerak bo'lganda temir preparatlarini qabul qilish

foydali bo'lishi mumkinligi xabar qilingan. Haddan tashqari yog 'iste'moli oksidlovchi stressni kuchaytirishi mumkin, shuning uchun miqdorga e'tibor berib, ketogenik parhezga antioksidant manbalarni kiritish tavsiya etiladi. Antioksidant manbalar sifatida yuqori darajadagi fenolik komponentlarni o'z ichiga oladi; Ratsionda yashil choy, oq choy, flavonoidlarga boy piyoz, pomidor, qizil mevalar, sitrus mevalari, quyuq sabzavotlar va lignanlarga boy to'liq donlarni ko'paytirish kerak.

Ketogenik parhez davomida uglevodlarni iste'mol qilishni cheklash orqali organizm taxminan 72 soatdan keyin tanaga kiradigan ketoz tizimida kimyoviy vositalar bilan energiya ishlab chiqarishni ko'paytirishga harakat qiladi va buning uchun ekzogen keton tuzlari va beta gidroksi butirat ishlatiladi. Beta gidroksi butirat va keton tuzlaridan foydalanish va ularning uzoq muddatli ta'siri bo'yicha yetarli ma'lumotlarning yo'qligi ularning ishonchligi bilan bog'liq ba'zi savollarni tug'diradi. Ushbu mavzu bo'yicha ko'proq ishlash kerak.

XULOSA

Ko'pgina tadqiqotlarda sportchilar uchun to'g'ri nazorat qilinadigan va rejalashtirilgan bugungi kunda mashhur dietalar, mashhur e'tiqodga qaramasdan, salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmasligi mumkinligi ta'kidlangan. Biroq, ko'pchilik sportchilar ovqatlanishni rejalashtirishda professional yordam olmaydilar va to'g'ri ovqatlanmaydilar, bu dietalarni tasodifiy ma'lumotlar bilan qo'llash salbiy oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin. Qisqa muddatli ijobiy natijalarga erishilgan bo'lsa-da, uzoq muddatda shikastlanish xavfining oshishi va chidamlilik qobiliyati va ishlashining pasayishi kuzatilishi mumkin. Agar sportchilar vegetarian, vegetarian, ketogen va intervalgacha ro'za tutish dietalarini qo'llashlari kerak bo'lsa, ular dietolog nazorati ostida va ma'lum parametrlarga rioya qilish orqali amalga oshirilishiga e'tibor berish kerak va ularni juda yaqin qilish hech qanday xavf tug'dirmasligi kerak. raqobatga. Ushbu parhezlarining uzoq muddatli ta'siri bo'yicha ko'proq tadqiqotlar bo'lmasa, har doim savollar bo'ladi.

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